

Motivation mediating effect on principals' personality, job satisfaction, and affective commitment

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Article Info

Article history:

Received Jan 24, 2023

Revised Oct 27, 2023

Accepted Nov 10, 2023

Keywords:

Affective commitment

Job satisfaction

Motivation

Personality

School principals

ABSTRACT

Affective commitment is ultimately carried out by a leader in an organization, including in high schools. This study mainly aims to examine the influence of personality and job satisfaction on the affective commitment of high school principals mediated by motivation. A quantitative survey was employed in this study. The sample studied was 90 public high school principals in Jakarta, Indonesia. The data were collected through a questionnaire, which has been tested for validity and reliability. The data were analyzed using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM) using SmartPLS 3.0 software. The results showed a significant relationship between the public school principals' personality and job satisfaction on their affective commitment which is mediated by motivation. In more detail, the results indicated: i) a positive direct effect of personality on affective commitment, personality on motivation, and job satisfaction on the motivation of public school principals; ii) no significant direct effect of job satisfaction on affective commitment; and iii) a mediating role of motivation, that directs to a positive and significant influence on personality, job satisfaction, and principals' affective commitment. The study's implications for related authorities are presented.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The current globalization era has required each organization including schools to upgrade the quality of human resources. Not to mention, it is a fact that the greatest asset of the organization is its human resources [1]. Education and its policies, as well as lifelong learning, play a crucial role in the productive age era since the quality of human resources is a result of the educational products that take place today. Human resource development and knowledge have relatively strict control over the quality of education [2].

In the interest of cultivating quality education, schools need to be operated and led by capable individuals who prioritize and appreciate their job at schools to fully utilize their human resource potential. In leading an educational institution, school principals play very crucial roles, as they are a party to engage in educational progress [3]. In this case, school principals as top leaders should have an acceptable affective commitment as it far outweighs obligation-based commitments [4].

In actuality, although school administrators are tasked with leading and directing the school endeavoring the improvement of educational quality, their devotion or dedication is occasionally questioned. More broadly, reports suggest that school principals in Indonesia lack the skills necessary to run and oversee their institutions, specifically leadership and management skills [5]. Going further, principals' weaknesses are in the monitoring and evaluation skills, technological competence, and ability to manage schools' facilities [6]. Given this reality, it is evident that a stronger commitment to managing schools is required. Further, school principals are required to maintain professional and moral affective commitments [7].

According to Meyer *et al.* [8], affective commitment as employees' feeling of attachment to their organization, will determine how well the employees perform their job [9]. This commitment will initially direct employees to work involvement or engagement [10]. It is examined that affective commitment might predict loyalty [11]. To these ends, affective commitment predicts many crucial elements to succeed in an organization including in educational institutions. In the context of this study, affective commitment will support school principals' efforts to raise academic standards.

Several elements that impact affective commitment are listed. First, affective commitment is affected by personality. It is reported that employees' affective commitment is mediated by behavior [12] as a part of personality. The development and implementation of innovative and high-quality instruction in schools are influenced by the school principals' personalities [13]. More specifically, it is proven that the qualities of personality are crucial in understanding how committed employees are to the company [14]. Personality also functions to make changes in employees' affective commitment [15].

Additionally, job satisfaction is also declared to affect affective commitment. It is an attitude to work [16], thus it becomes a critical point as job satisfaction will either predict work performance [17] or motivation [18]. Employees who work satisfactorily will feel an attachment to their organization. In the end, the inclination for satisfied employees to give their best work is obvious. Successful content educators, including teachers and school principals who manage educational institutions, are more inclined to give their all to enhancing the educational system and advancing society as a whole [19].

It is either claimed that motivation is a factor in determining affective commitment. Work motivation shall direct employees to be committed to their organization [20]. Additionally, motivation is reported to affect employees' commitment to their affective organization which is specifically moderated by voice behavior [21]. Deepening the analysis, motivation intrinsically has a moderating effect on affective commitment [22]. In terms of collaborative work, the enhancement of team members' affective commitment is another claim made [23].

Previous studies have demonstrated how each element has its own impact on affective commitment. Meanwhile, this current study seeks to determine the degree to which school principals' affective commitment is influenced by personality and work motivation by the mediation of motivation. Then, this study formulates a research question, "Is the affective commitment of public-school principals influenced by personality and job satisfaction through the mediation of motivation?". To answer this question, a survey method is employed. It is projected that the findings would help policymakers create a positive work environment where school principals can execute the best of their abilities. Correspondingly, the results of the study are expected to upgrade the professionalism of high school principals in their dedication to the schools they lead.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

The main objective of this study is to examine the influence of personality and job satisfaction on the affective commitment of high school principals by the mediation of motivation. To address the objective, the current study employed survey research with a quantitative approach. Data analysis using Partial Least Square Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM). To examine the direct effect among three variables, the model is proposed: exogen variables consist of personality (x_1), job satisfaction (x_2), and motivation (x_3), while endogen variables consist of affective commitment (y).

The research was conducted in Jakarta's public high schools. The accessible population is all public high school principals in Jakarta comprising 117 persons. A simple random sampling technique was utilized, in which 90 samples were then assigned using the Slovin formula for sample size.

This study addressed the research question: "Is there any statistically significant direct influence of personality, and job satisfaction by the mediation of motivation towards principals' affective commitment at the public high schools in Jakarta?". Accordingly, the following hypotheses can be formulated as: i) Personality influences affective commitment of public-school principals (H1); ii) Job satisfaction influences affective commitment of public-school principals (H2); iii) Personality influences the motivation of public-school principals (H3); iv) Job satisfaction influences the motivation of public-school principals (H4); v) Motivation influences affective commitment of public-school principals (H5); vi) Personality and job satisfaction mediated by motivation influence the affective commitment of public-school principals (H6).

To get a comprehensive representation of how the variables presented are related, a constellation model is drawn. This model might guide the researchers in mapping the probability emerging from all variables. The scheme of the all-variable hypotheses is illustrated in Figure 1.

The empirical data related to variables were obtained through a questionnaire (close-ended). The questionnaire was arranged based on the exogen and endogen variables. Each question is scaled using the Likert scale model and scored from 1-5. The questionnaire range is 1 for “never”, 2 for “seldom,” 3 for “sometimes,” 4 for “often,” and 5 for “always”. For data analysis, the Partial Least Squares (PLS) Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) technique run with Smart PLS version 3.0 was used in this study. As an SEM method, PLS assists in analyzing the models of structural measurement and the associated paths.

Figure 1. The constellation model

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Results

3.1.1. Respondent characteristics

The current study involved 90 public school principals as the research participants. All of them come from administrative regencies and cities in the area of Jakarta. The characteristics of the participants are presented in Table 1.

The public-school principals were selected based on the following criteria: a working area, education, age, and working period. The working area of the respondents consists of six areas covering Central Jakarta, West Jakarta, East Jakarta, North Jakarta, South Jakarta, and Seribu Island, in which the most respondents come from East Jakarta (34.4%) and the least are from Seribu Island (1.1%). From the criterion of education level, the public-school principals possess bachelor, master, and doctoral degrees, which the most come from master’s degrees (71.1%), and doctoral degrees (2.2%). Based on their age, the criterion is chosen with the following range: 46-50, 51-55, and 56-60 years old, in which most of the principals are between 51-55 years old (45.6%). The last criterion is the working period, which covers 7-17, 18-28, and 29-39 years, in which the most come from 18-28 years of working (60%).

Table 1. The respondents’ characteristics

	Criteria	Count	%
Working area	Central Jakarta	10	11.1
	West Jakarta	13	14.4
	East Jakarta	31	34.4
	North Jakarta	13	14.4
	South Jakarta	22	24.4
	Seribu Island	1	1.1
Education	Bachelor	24	26.7
	Master	64	71.1
	Doctor	2	2.2
Age	46-50 years old	28	31.1
	51-55 years old	41	45.6
	56-60 years old	21	23.3
Working period	7-17 years	1	1.1
	18-28 years	54	60.0
	29-39 years	35	38.9

3.1.2. Indicator testing

a. Construct reliability dan validity test

There are two phases of tests to perform at the beginning of testing indicators. The first is testing the construct reliability, the next one is the validity test. The results of the two tests are presented in Table 2. The construction should have an average variance extracted (AVE) of 0.5 to achieve satisfactory results. The internal consistency testing is Cronbach alpha; the lower accepted coefficient limit for Cronbach alpha is

0.70. Table 2 demonstrates that each research instrument used to measure the exogenous variables (affective commitment, personality, job satisfaction, and motivation) met the reliability and validity requirements. It was evident in the scores of Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability for each variable, which were more than 0.70, and the AVE score, which was above 0.50. All latent variables measured in this study have Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability values greater than 0.7, so it can be said that all latent variables can be considered reliable.

Table 2. The results of the construct reliability and validity test

Variable	Cronbach's Alpa	Composite reliability	AVE	Predicate
Affective commitment	0.954	0.961	0.711	Reliable and valid
Personality	0.992	0.992	0.930	Reliable and valid
Job satisfaction	0.989	0.990	0.928	Reliable and valid
Motivation	0.978	0.981	0.836	Reliable and valid

b. Discriminant validity test

Having checked the construct reliability and validity, the discriminant should also be validated. To check the validity of the discriminant, the test of heterotrait-monotrait (HTMT) is applied. The results are reported in Table 3. For the determination of the validity of discriminants (heterotrait-monotrait), it is necessary to analyze the value of discrimination for variables. The value should not be greater than 0.9. Table 3 shows the HTMT score for most constructs that met the discriminant validity criteria, which is less than 0.90. The variables of personality, job satisfaction, and motivation achieve an HTML ratio of more than 0.90. Therefore, all three do not meet the validity of the discriminant.

Table 3. The results of the HTMT test

Variable	Affective commitment	Job satisfaction	Motivation	Personality
Affective commitment	0.843			
Job satisfaction	0.564	0.964		
Motivation	0.636		0.963	
Personality	0.659	0.680	0.527	0.914

3.1.3. Hypothesis testing

a. Path coefficients/direct effect

After confirming the measurement model's reliability and validity, the structural model's assessment needs to be calculated. The first test is the path coefficient test to determine the direct effect of the variables. The results of the test model are put forward in Table 4.

Table 4. The results of the path coefficient test

Variable	Original	Sample mean	Standard deviation	T statistics	P values	Hypothesis
Personality – Motivation	0.418	0.418	0.117	3.578	0.000	Accepted
Personality – Affective commitment	0.371	0.369	0.099	3.761	0.000	Accepted
Motivation – Affective commitment	0.338	0.341	0.091	3.721	0.000	Accepted
Job satisfaction - Motivation	0.308	0.302	0.108	2.849	0.005	Accepted
Job satisfaction – Affective commitment	0.112	0.112	0.110	1.017	0.309	Rejected

The value of the t-test is obtained, and the significance of the causal relationship is confirmed based on the path coefficient and t-statistical measurements. A hypothesis showing relationships between variables is accepted if the path coefficient for statistics-t is above 1.96 and the p-value is less than 0.05. To be more specific, first, personality → motivation reached the patch coefficient of 0.418 with t-statistics of 3.578 and a p-value of 0.000, meaning that personality has a positive and significant influence on motivation. Second, personality → affective commitment reached the path coefficient of 0.371 with t-statistics 3.761 and p-value of 0.000, meaning that personality has a positive and significant influence on affective commitment. Third, the path coefficient of motivation → affective commitment was 0.338, with a t-statistic of 3.721 and a p-value of 0.000, indicating that motivation has a positive and significant influence on affective commitment. Fourth, job satisfaction → motivation reached the path coefficient of 0.308 with t-statistics 2.849 and a p-value of 0.000, meaning that motivation has a positive and significant influence on affective commitment. Fifth, the path coefficient for job satisfaction affective commitment was 0.112, with t-statistics of 1.017 and a p-value of 0.309, indicating that conceptual job satisfaction has no significant influence on affective commitment.

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b. Indirect effect analysis

Projecting the indirect effect among the variables is also significant to see the complete effects among them. To check such an effect, testing the indirect influence of job satisfaction and personality is carried out. The results are reported in Table 5. The results of indirect influences indicate two points. Firstly, there is an indirect influence of job satisfaction on affective commitment because the p-value is 0.02. This implies that motivation, as the intervening variable, mediates the principals' affective commitment. Secondly, there is an indirect influence of personality on affective commitment due to the p-value of 0.02. The result indicated that motivation, as the intervening variable, mediates the personality and affective commitment of the principals.

Table 5. The results of indirect effect analysis

Variable	Original	Sample mean	Standard deviation	T statistics	P values	Hypothesis
Job satisfaction – Affective commitment	0.10	0.10	0.05	2.27	0.02	Significant
Personality – Affective commitment	0.14	0.14	0.06	2.32	0.02	Significant

c. R-square score evaluation

The last to calculate is determining the value of the R-square evaluation. The R-square used in this study is R-square adjusted because it has more than one exogenous variable. The results are summarized in Table 6. According to the table, the R-square I adjustment path is 0.51. This implies that personality and job satisfaction influence affective commitment by up to 51%, which is categorized as significant. While the II path achieves 0.43. This further means that personality and job satisfaction influence motivation by up to 43%. This relationship, then, can be interpreted as weak. The relationships among variables are further illustrated in Figure 2.

Table 6. R-square

Variable	R Square	Square adjusted
Affective commitment	0.52	0.51
Motivation	0.44	0.43

Figure 2. The scheme for the relations among research variables

3.2. Discussion

3.2.1. Personality influencing affective commitment of public-school principals

Hypothesis 1 (H1) intends to determine how personality influences the affective commitment of public-school principals. The result of the path coefficient proves that H1, stating that personality influences the affective commitment of public-school principals, is accepted because the score is 0.371 with a t-statistic of 3.761 and a p-value of 0.000. The finding indicates that the school principals' personality determines directly their affective commitment. Previous research reported that personality is also proven to directly and significantly enhance employees' affective commitment [24]. Performing a more detailed analysis, the result of the current study highlights that personality traits consisting of openness, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness dan neuroticism, might specify the emotional attachment of the principals to their schools. Corresponding to the results, conscientiousness, neuroticism, and openness are proven to be a measurement of employees' commitment to their organization [25].

3.2.2. Job satisfaction influencing affective commitment of public-school principals

Hypothesis 2 (H2) is formulated to see the impact of job satisfaction on the affective commitment of public-school principals. The statistical calculation shows that H2, formulated as job satisfaction influences the affective commitment of public-school principals, is rejected because the score is 0.112 with t-statistics 1.017 and p-value 0.309. The regression does not confirm a significant effect of job satisfaction on the principals' affective commitment. The finding is contrary to the reports that the impact of job satisfaction on affective commitment is also visible in the context of employees performing their commitment when giving service to customers [26] and mediated by facilitating the work environment [27]. In the context of schooling, school principals' commitment should be performed when accommodating students' educational demands whether or not they feel content with their job and working atmosphere.

3.2.3. Personality influencing motivation of public-school principals

Hypothesis 3 (H3) tries to seek the answer to how personality gives influence on the motivation of public-school principals. The calculation of the path coefficient indicates that H3, declaring that personality impacts the motivation of public-school principals, is accepted because the score is 0.418 with t-statistics 0.117 and p-value 0.000. The result describes that personality impacts the principals' motivation directly and significantly. The personal qualities of the principals are expected to incite them to give their utmost for the schools' quality advancement. Emotional stability, level of offensiveness, and types of personality are reported to give an impact on work motivation [28]. The positive relation between personality and motivation is also revealed regarding personality traits like agreeableness, conscientiousness, and openness [29].

3.2.4. Job satisfaction influencing motivation of public-school principals

Hypothesis 4 (H4) is proposed to examine the effect of job satisfaction on the motivation of public-school principals. The path coefficient calculation result presents that H4, hypothesized that job satisfaction influences the motivation of public-school principals, is accepted because the score is 0.338 with t-statistics 2.849 and a p-value of 0.005. This explicitly declares that job satisfaction has a direct impact on the principals' motivation. Their work drive will be encouraged once they feel content in their position. Previous research has also discovered that job satisfaction is directly and positively related to work motivation [30], [31]. Portraying a more detailed element, self-determination is a determining factor in the relation of job satisfaction and motivation [32].

3.2.5. Motivation influencing affective commitment of public-school principals

Hypothesis 5 (H5) is formulated to determine the effect of public-school principals' motivation on their affective commitment. The path analysis proves that H5, which is structured as motivation influences affective commitment of public-school principals, is accepted because the score is 0.308 with t-statistics of 3.721 and a p-value of 0.000. The hypothesis testing result suggests a significant direct effect of motivation on affective commitment. When the principals are encouraged to perform the best job for the schools, in the end, they will feel attached to their schools and identify their sense of belonging. In a wider scope, motivation either gives a strong positive impact on organizational commitment [20] including affective commitment within. Another research reported a bit different result, listing that employees' motivation is indirectly influenced by affective commitment [33].

3.2.6. Personality and job satisfaction's influence on affective commitment mediated by motivation

The analysis and interpretation of R-square adjusted results in several points. The R-adjusted path I model scored 0.51, which means that the variables (personality and job satisfaction) simultaneously influence affective commitment up to 51%, categorized as substantial (strong). Meanwhile, the path II model scored 0.43, which means that personality and job satisfaction, as well as motivation, simultaneously influence

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affective commitment up to 43%, categorized as weak. Briefly saying, motivation serves as a significant mediating factor. Reports on previous research have also found that motivation has a moderating role in affective commitment [34], [35]. Motivation also moderates the relationship between affective commitment and another variable such as transformational leadership [36].

4. CONCLUSION

The ability to emotionally connect to the institutions where they work is a driving force for public school leaders. As a deciding factor in achieving the educational goals of the schools in the future, this kind of devotion is essential to have. To effectively govern and lead the schools, school principals should continue to embrace the idea that they can only advance their institutions by dedicating themselves to their schools. The current study has examined how personality, job satisfaction, and motivation have impacted the school principals' affective commitment. It signifies a direct effect among the variables studied. First, there is a positive direct effect of personality on affective commitment, personality on motivation, and job satisfaction on the motivation of public-school principals. Second, there is no significant direct effect of job satisfaction on affective commitment. Third, the current study also notices a mediating effect of motivation that directs to a positive significant effect of personality and job satisfaction on the principals' affective commitment.

This study further implies that the authorities treat the principals with greater decency, exoneration, and morality integration in order to build their personalities and foster school principals' emotional commitment. Giving the principals opportunities for equal treatment and job progression may help bring about the realization. Regarding satisfaction at work, giving the principals enough stimulation for their thrilled feelings concerning their jobs, and co-workers, receiving appreciation, and opportunities for self-development will help to increase affective commitment by encouraging job satisfaction. The authorities are adamant about giving them the room and chances they need to develop and raise their academic performance. Withal, future research on how personality, job satisfaction, and motivation impact other dimensions of organizational commitment (normative and continuance) is highly recommended in the pursuit of the ideal development of quality school management.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to thank all public-school principals in the Provincial Education Board of DKI Jakarta who have provided excellent responses and warm cooperation during the research.

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